
A Study of Population Migration with reference to Sangli District

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ABSTRACT:

Migration is very important phenomena in human geography. All over the world this process is effects on various physical as well as human aspects. The present study focuses on migration which is from rural to urban area. Due to migration of working population from the study area only children and old population remains. It impacts on entire economic, social structure of the area. Impact is also seen on population density, age structure, gender ratio economic status, living of standard. There are some serious social problems also generated. Migration of young age group from Sangli tehsil is higher they spends long duration of time from their native place with wife, children and other family members.

The objective of this study is to call attention towards this problem. The researcher also tries to minimize and solve this problem at some extent by giving suggestions. This area has a potential for tourism and some crops like rice. Researcher suggests the planning and management for develop the tourism facilities so the people get the work and jobs hare. Taking into consideration the social aspects of the problem can also be solved at some extent.

Keywords: Migration Meaning, Population Migration Pattern, Causes etc.

Introduction:

Migration is a geographical phenomenon which concerned to population of any geographical area. When an individual or group of individuals moves from one place to another, for lesser or longer duration or permanently, from one political boundary to another, this movement is called as migration. This may happen in a pre-planned manner or may happen suddenly. Also it can be either voluntary or involuntary.

In general, migration brings changes in the population. If people migrate to be a region the population of the region will increase. If people leave a region and migrate to another region, its population will decrease. Population density, patterns and

structure of the population of both the original region (donor region) and the region where migration has taken place (recipient region) will be affected.

Migration is migrating in different parts of the world since their evolution on earth for better and secure life. Migration is not merely shift of people from one place to another, as it is most fundamental to the understanding of continuously changing space content and space relationship of an area (Gosal G.S. 1961). The term 'Mobility' is also used to define migration, but it includes both 'circulation' and 'Migration'. Circulation has been defined as short term repetitive and cyclical movement of people with no intension of permanent changes of residence, migration implies permanent

change of residence. (Horney, William and Jones, Melvyn 1980).

Objectives of the Study:

Migration is an important aspect of the study of Population Geography. This study is carried out in Sangli district of Maharashtra with following objectives:

1. To study the Population migration pattern of Sangli District.
2. To study the causes of population Migration of Sangli District.

Methodology:

This study is totally based on the secondary data collected from different sources. Along with data is collected with different government and nongovernment organizations in Sangli district of Maharashtra. The data is collected, processed and tabulated for study purpose. The interpretation of data is done with geographical point of view.

Review of Literature:

Samuel., Johnson M. (1990): Pattern of female migration in Tamilnadu.

In Tamilnadu, women propensity to migrate is rising faster than that of man. Economic factors taking greater role in migration as well as life style, living standard, marriage, cultural and family factor too.

Upadhye., Chavan, V. D. (1991): A socio-economic survey of immigrant labor in brick –making industry in the Sangli district.

In this study author divided migration patterns into two categories that inter-district and another inter-state. In which inter-district migration pattern is more prevalent than inter-state migration because of socio-cultural and linguistic as well as administrative considerations.

Tawade M.D., Pardeshi P.B. (1993): The population Geography of Solapur district

In this study author says that, the region is the main cause of migration. Geographically region has large land resource potential but regional development due to adverse relief is the major cause for pushing the population out in the region. Undulating topography, hill range forming low table land, watershed area, uncertainty of job, scarcity of job generation, landless population are push factors

Jadhav Maruti Vithoba (2003): Satara District: A study in population Geography

Migratory movements are the products of social, cultural, economic, political and physical circumstances, in which individuals and societies find themselves. In Satara district highest growth rate observed than the next decade because in this decade formation of MIDC and establish government offices of immigration in 1981-2001 naturally increases migration.

Kale S.S. (2005): Seasonal migration of sugarcane cutters in Kolhapur District Maharashtra: A Geographical analysis.

This study focuses on seasonal migration. In this study we found that the standard of living of migrants is very low. These migrants get defiantly work for some period and after the end of season they get advance amount for next season. Therefore this option becomes more and more secure, and thus attract the people who don't want to take risk to find out new employment opportunity, maintain contacts with sugar factories or contractors.

Shiddappa Madar,(2008): Lambanis out migration from Vijayapura district of Karnataka.

In this study author focused on the major cause of the out migration. In this area heavy rainfall and irregular payment, low wages rate are the main causes for working outside their native place. The wages provided in other places which is higher when compared locally.

**Mujymdar Kar, Suparna,(2018):
Migration to Bengaluru study of return
migration of IT professionals.**

In this study author found that the process involved in return migration within a framework that has elements of macro and meso levels. In which family, community, industries and area are included. Difference between international wages and local wages also caused for migration. The IT sector, optimize these talented and skilled professionals and allows for a high degree of geographical mobility.

**Ingale V.B. (2019): A Geographical study
of Demographical characteristics in
Osmanabad district of Maharashtra state:**

In this study researcher goes very particularly. He used the Rees technique to describe the demographic characteristics of Osmanabad district. This area has a typical location. Due drought area there are limitations on development. Because of this, people goes toward cities and other developed area for jobs and any type of employment. This is the important factor for out migration.

Population Migration Pattern:

As the population is mostly rural based agriculture related to activities is the main source of employment in the district. The classification of the workers in the district is as given below:-

Sr. No.	Occupation	No. of Workers
1	Cultivators	354
2	Small & Marginal Farmers	309
3	Agricultural labours	197
4	Artisans	12
5	Household cottage industries	11
6	Allied Agro activities	17
7	Other workers	238

Sangli district is most economically developed district in Maharashtra. All economic activities from primary to quaternary are carried out in district, but these are concentrating in specific regions. Economic development can be seen in agriculture, industry and services.

Inter-State Migration Pattern in Sangli District:

Sangli district has emerged as an economic growth center in Maharashtra state, which attracts migrants from other states in large number. TableNo.3 shows the inter-state immigration patterns of workers.

State	Total	%	Male	%	Female	%
Jammu & Kashmir	48	0.15	30	0.13	18	0.19
Himachal Pradesh	6	0.02	2	0.01	4	0.04
Punjab	115	0.35	65	0.28	50	0.53
Chandigarh	6	0.02	5	0.02	1	0.01
Uttarakhand	20	0.06	10	0.04	10	0.11
Haryana	65	0.20	41	0.18	24	0.25
NCT of Delhi	99	0.30	51	0.22	48	0.51
Rajasthan	939	2.89	562	2.44	377	3.98
Uttar Pradesh	1,571	4.83	941	4.09	630	6.65
Bihar	615	1.89	443	1.92	172	1.82
Sikkim	1	0	1	0	0	0
Arunachal Pradesh	6	0.02	3	0.01	3	0.03

Nagaland	2	0.01	1	0	1	0.01
Manipur	2	0.01	1	0	1	0.01
Mizoram	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tripura	1	0	0	0	1	0.01
Meghalaya	1	0	0	0	1	0.01
Assam	37	0.11	24	0.10	13	0.14
West Bengal	499	1.54	329	1.43	170	1.79
Jharkhand	90	0.28	60	0.26	30	0.32
Odisha	181	0.56	143	0.62	38	0.40
Chhattisgarh	105	0.32	40	0.17	65	0.69
Madhya Pradesh	419	1.29	252	1.09	167	1.76
Gujarat	798	2.46	305	1.33	493	5.20
Daman & Diu	1	0	1	0	0	0
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	2	0.01	2	0.01	0	0
Andhra Pradesh	674	2.07	356	1.55	318	3.36
Karnataka	25,462	78.36	19,001	82.55	6461	68.19
Goa	178	0.55	69	0.30	109	1.15
Lakshadweep	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kerala	289	0.89	157	0.68	132	1.39
Tamil Nadu	257	0.79	122	0.53	135	1.42
Puducherry	1	0	0	0	1	0.01
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	3	0.01	1	0	2	0.02
Total	32493	100	23018	100	9475	100

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Above table shows that the, there were total 32493 persons recorded as migrants in Sangli district in 2011 in that 23018 male and 9475 females population is observed. Persons from every State and union territory are migrated towards Sangli district for economic purpose excluding Lakshadweep. In this migration pattern male population was highly migrated as compare to female population because for work sex specific migration is observed and where always male dominances is seen. As workers have tendency to travel for short distance, we can see labors from neighboring states like Karnataka have migrated to the district in more number.

According to 2011 census, Migrants form Karnataka ranks first with 25,462 persons (78.36%), followed by Uttar Pradesh with 1,571 (4.83%) persons, Rajasthan with 939 (2.89%) persons, Gujarat

with 798 (2.46%) persons, Andhra Pradesh with 674 (2.07) persons, Bihar with 615 (1.89%), West Bengal with 499 (1.54%) persons, Madhya Pradesh with 419 (1.29%) persons, Kerala with 289 (0.89%), Tamil Nadu 257(0.79%) persons and Goa with 178 (0.55%). Persons from North-eastern states like Arunachal Pradesh, Nagaland, Manipur, Mizoram, Meghalaya, etc. are very lass. There are only 50 migrants recorded out of 30 male and 30 females.

Migrants from Karnataka, Uttar Pradesh and Rajasthan are mainly engaged in construction works like brickwork, centering, coloring, flooring etc. Workers from Bihar as well as West Bengal provide cheap labors for industries. Many Gujarati population is engaged in textile industry of the district.

Mainly male migrates to far distance for jobs, services, business and education.

Women have social restrictions and responsibility therefore the share of women migrants was less comparing to men in every state in-migrant.

Inter-District Migration Pattern in Sangli District:

Inter-district migration is the outcome of regional imbalance in economic development. The Maharashtra state is

economically progressed in India, but that development is not equally distributed in all districts of the state. The districts of western Maharashtra are highly developed whereas Konkan region along with Vidarbha are moderately progressed, but district of Marathwada, Khandesh are economically backward.

District	Total	%	Male	%	Female	%
Nandurbar	148	0.06	77	0.05	71	0.09
Dhule	429	0.18	226	0.15	203	0.25
Jalgaon	646	0.27	342	0.22	304	0.37
Buldana	207	0.09	109	0.07	98	0.12
Akola	254	0.11	133	0.09	121	0.15
Washim	74	0.03	41	0.03	33	0.04
Amravati	229	0.10	121	0.08	108	0.13
Wardha	95	0.04	49	0.03	46	0.06
Nagpur	460	0.19	235	0.15	225	0.27
Bhandara	54	0.02	29	0.02	25	0.03
Gondiya	36	0.02	20	0.01	16	0.02
Gadchiroli	11	0.00	5	0.00	6	0.01
Chandrapur	63	0.03	28	0.02	35	0.04
Yavatmal	236	0.10	138	0.09	98	0.12
Nanded	401	0.17	214	0.14	187	0.23
Hingoli	73	0.03	37	0.02	36	0.04
Parbhani	1,963	0.82	1,018	0.65	945	1.14
Jalna	910	0.38	477	0.31	433	0.52
Aurangabad	432	0.18	236	0.15	196	0.24
Nashik	926	0.39	524	0.34	402	0.49
Thane	1,798	0.75	1,027	0.66	771	0.93
Mumbai (Suburban)	3	0.00	3	0.00	0	0.00
Mumbai	10,906	4.58	6,049	3.88	4,857	5.88
Raigarh	470	0.20	265	0.17	205	0.25
Pune	9,928	4.17	6,013	3.86	3,915	4.74
Ahmadnagar	2,622	1.10	1,330	0.85	1,292	1.56
Bid	11,911	5.00	6,270	4.03	5,641	6.83
Latur	1,155	0.48	623	0.40	532	0.64
Osmanabad	2,071	0.87	1,008	0.65	1,063	1.29
Solapur	50,365	21.13	33,431	21.47	16,934	20.50
Satara	58,391	24.50	40,740	26.16	17,651	21.37
Ratnagiri	2,796	1.17	1,518	0.97	1,278	1.55
Sindhudurg	862	0.36	473	0.30	389	0.47
Kolhapur	77,411	32.48	52,919	33.98	24,492	29.65
Total	238,336	100	155,728	100	82,608	100

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The scenario of inter-district in-migration in Sangli district (2011) is shown in table 4. Table no.4 indicates that people

from all districts of Maharashtra state had migrated towards Sangli district in more or less number. The highest inter-district in-

migrant in Sangli district was observed from Kolhapur district with 77411 total persons accounts 32.48 % of all migrant which was followed by Satara district with 24.50 % and Solapur district with 21.13%. It is observed that 78.11 % inter-district migration is produced from surrounding district i.e. Kolhapur, Satara and Solapur district.

Total 11,911 (5%) person are migrated from Bid district which are basically working in the agricultural sector. It is also observed that people from Mumbai with 10,906 persons (4.58%), Pune with 9,928 persons (4.17%), Ratnagiri with 2,796 persons (1.17) and Ahmadnagar with 2,622 persons (1.10%) has moderate migration.

People from remote districts such as Nandurbar, Dhule, Jalgaon, Buldana, Akola, Washim, Amravati, Wardha, Nagpur, Bhandara, Gondiya, Gadchiroli, Chandrapur, Yavatmal, Nanded, Hingoli, Jalna and Aurangabad district has very less.

Inter-district emigration data clearly indicates that migrants have a tendency to migrate for short distance. Sangli district is an important district in western Maharashtra, which is developed in agriculture, industry, trade, transport and services. Many migrants from neighboring district come to Sangli district in search of jobs, services, business, education, etc.

Causes of population Migration of Sangli District:

There are different reasons for human migration from one region to another. It can be economic reasons in some places and social causes in some places.

1) Physical:

Natural events like earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, droughts and flooding may be responsible for population to migrate.

Natural Disasters: People may move to escape natural disasters like floods or droughts.

Climate Change: People may move to

escape the impact of climate change.

2) Economic:

Migration in which people migrate in search of jobs, businesses, improve their standard of living, etc.

Lack of opportunities: People may move to find work, improve their economic status, or escape poverty.

Poor labor standards: People may move to find better employment opportunities or higher wages.

Unemployment: People may move to find work or escape unemployment.

3) Social:

Often people have to migrate forcefully. People decide to leave the place rather than face social problems. It may involve forcing people of a certain group to migrate. Discrimination, education, health, medical facilities, marriage, etc. can be reasons behind migration.

Family: People may move to join family or be closer to friends.

Culture: People may move to live in a place with a familiar culture.

4) Political:

Sometimes war or political problems may arise in a country. In that case, people from that country migrate and seek refuge in another country.

Political persecution: People may move to escape political persecution or war.

Human rights violations: People may move to escape large-scale human rights violations.

Conclusion:

The study of migration is a most important aspect of population change after, fertility & mortality. Sangli district has fertile soil & adequate supply of water for the development of agriculture. So, there is development of sugar industry and agro based industry, which attracts large amount of seasonal migrants in the district. There are other different reasons for human migration from

one region to another region. Due to physical, economic, social and political factors effect on in migration and out migration of sangli district. In drought, flood, Unfertile soil, undulating physiographical reasons out migration have done like Shirala, Jat, Khanapur and Atpadi.

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